

Enhanced Reactivity and Selective Adsorption: Unveiling the Potential of Metal-Decorated Graphene Membranes for Biosensing

Hazem Abdelsalam^{1,2*}, Mahmoud A.S. Sakr^{3*}, Vasil A. Saroka^{4,5,6}, Ghada M Abdelrazek³, Omar H. Abd-Elkader⁷, Nahed H. Teieb^{1,8}, Yushen Liu⁹, Qinfang Zhang^{1*}

¹ School of Materials Science and Engineering, Yancheng Institute of Technology, Yancheng 224051, PR China

²Theoretical Physics Department, National Research Centre, El-Buhouth Str., 12622, Dokki, Giza, Egypt

³Center of Basic Science (CBS), Misr University of Science and Technology (MUST), 6th October City, Egypt

⁴Department of Physics, University of Rome Tor Vergata and INFN, Via della Ricerca Scientifica 1, 00133, Roma, Italy

⁵Institute for Nuclear Problems, Belarusian State University, Bobruiskaya 11, 220030, Minsk, Belarus

⁶TBpack Ltd., 27 Old Gloucester Street, London WC1N 3AX, UK

⁷Department of Physics and Astronomy, College of Science, King Saud University, P.O. Box 2455, Riyadh 11451, Saudi Arabia

⁸Electron Microscope and Thin Films Department, National Research Centre, El-Buhouth Str., 12622, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

⁹Yancheng Polytechnic College, Yancheng 224005, China

Abstract

This study investigates the structural, stability, electronic, and optical properties of finite graphene membranes through a comprehensive computational analysis. The 2D membranes are constructed from hexagonal graphene quantum dots and are decorated with Co, Mn, and Ni. Stability assessments, based on binding energies, affirm the stable formation of the 2D membrane and its derivatives. Electronic investigations reveal a reduction in the energy gap upon metal decoration, indicating enhanced reactivity. Membrane studies demonstrate effective adsorption of creatinine and uric acid on both edge and surface sites, supported by negative adsorption energies. Electronic transitions and absorption spectra shifts indicate dynamic interactions, emphasizing the materials' potential for selective molecular separation. Non-covalent interaction analysis confirmed the role of van der Waals interactions in creatinine and uric acid adsorption. Overall, the findings suggest that the graphene membrane and its decorated derivatives hold promise for selective adsorption applications, especially in the context of biosensing.

Keywords: Graphene nanodots; 2D Membranes; Metal-Decoration; DFT: Electronic Properties; creatinine and uric acid sensing.

1. Introduction

Two-dimensional (2D) materials, exemplified by graphene, transition metal dichalcogenides, and black phosphorus, have garnered considerable attention owing to their distinctive properties and

wide-ranging applications [1]. Graphene, characterized by a thin sheet of carbon atoms arranged in a honeycomb lattice, showcases exceptional mechanical, electrical, and thermal attributes, positioning it as a highly promising material for diverse applications, including electronics, energy storage, and sensors [2,3]. Similarly, transition metal dichalcogenides like molybdenum disulfide and tungsten diselenide have emerged as prospective candidates for electronic and optoelectronic applications, attributed to their direct bandgap and strong light-matter interactions [4]. Black phosphorus, with its anisotropic properties, demonstrates potential in applications such as transistors, photodetectors, and energy storage devices [5]. The distinctive features of 2D materials render them promising for a broad spectrum of applications, and ongoing research in this field is advancing rapidly.

Extensively researched for their size-dependent properties and potential in optoelectronics and photonics, two-dimensional (2D) quantum dots, essentially 2D nanocrystals, have garnered significant interest [6,7]. These quantum dots exhibit quantum confinement in two dimensions, resulting in discrete energy levels and customizable optical properties [8,9]. In contrast to their three-dimensional counterparts, 2D quantum dots boast a larger surface-to-volume ratio, enhancing their surface chemistry and providing greater control over their optical and electronic characteristics [10,11]. Moreover, the facile integration of 2D quantum dots with other 2D materials, such as graphene and transition metal dichalcogenides, for hybrid nanodevice applications is feasible [12–14]. Research in this domain is rapidly progressing, with 2D quantum dots showing immense promise in areas such as solar cells, light-emitting diodes, and quantum computing.

Two-dimensional (2D) porous materials, exemplified by graphene oxide, have exhibited considerable potential in the realm of wastewater treatment, owing to their high surface area, adjustable pore size, and remarkable adsorption capabilities [15]. Graphene oxide membranes have proven effective in removing heavy metal ions, organic dyes, and pharmaceuticals from wastewater [16]. Additionally, 2D covalent and metal-organic frameworks have emerged as promising materials for contaminant removal from water, attributed to their high porosity and surface area [17,18]. These materials can be easily synthesized with tailored chemical properties and pore sizes, facilitating selective adsorption of specific contaminants from wastewater [19]. Furthermore, 2D porous materials have been instrumental in the development of membrane technology for wastewater treatment, showcasing the potential for scalable production and application [20]. Overall, the potential of 2D porous materials for efficient and selective removal of contaminants from wastewater is significant, and ongoing research in this field is making rapid strides.

2D nanomaterials influence cells mechanically, electrochemically, or chemically [21]. Mechanical effects depend on hydrophobicity, bending stiffness, and structure. Electromechanical interactions involve catalytic features, generating reactive oxygen species (ROS) and inducing oxidative stress, a key factor in cytotoxicity [22]. Chemical interactions release molecules and atoms, originating from bioactive molecules or nanomaterial decomposition [21]. Understanding these mechanisms

is crucial for tailoring 2D nanomaterials for biomedical applications, addressing uncertainties in their impact on cytotoxicity. Assays, such as Dichloro-dihydro-fluorescein diacetate (DCFH-DA) for ROS, Alamar Blue for proliferation, layered double hydroxide (LDH) for membrane integrity, and gene expression studies, provide detailed insights. Research on long-term exposure is vital for transitioning technology from the lab to the consumer market [23].

Proteins undergo metabolism in the liver, leading to the production of waste materials that are transported to the kidneys for disposal, with a primary focus on urea and creatinine elimination [24]. The kidneys play vital roles in toxin removal, mineral balance, red blood cell production, and maintaining acid-base equilibrium [25]. Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) develops when the kidneys fail to efficiently eliminate urea and creatinine, progressing to End-Stage Renal Disease (ESRD) when renal function drops below 10% [26]. While dialysis and kidney transplantation are common treatments, there are limitations [27]. Wearable Artificial Kidneys (WAKs) present a promising alternative, offering improved patient mobility and quality of life [28]. Ongoing research is exploring the use of 2D materials as effective urea and creatinine adsorbents for WAKs, employing density functional theory (DFT) for detailed atomistic analyses.

Our research utilizes density functional theory to explore the structural, electronic, and optical characteristics of 4AHEX and its metal-decorated derivatives (Co, Mn, Ni) as potential membrane materials. We uncover subtle alterations in molecular geometry induced by metal decoration, along with heightened reactivity, suggesting applications in catalysis and materials science. Electronic analyses reveal a narrowed energy gap, indicating potential for selective adsorption, particularly of creatinine and uric acid. Calculated binding energies confirm stability, emphasizing the originality and suitability of these materials for membrane-based molecular separation. Overall, our study positions 4AHEX and its derivatives as original and promising contenders for various applications, including water purification and medical diagnostics. Co, Mn, and Ni were chosen as dopants for 2D 4AHEX membranes due to their availability, reactivity, and potential applications. While their safety in biological applications should be considered, the choice of dopant ultimately depends on specific application requirements and safety considerations. Other transition metals like Fe could also be considered depending on their suitability for the intended application.

2. Computational Methodology

In this work, we use density functional theory (DFT) simulations using Gaussian 16 to investigate the optimized structures, electrical properties, optical behaviors, and membrane applications of finite graphene membranes [29]. To ensure a comprehensive representation of the system, the hybrid B3LYP functional [30,31] is employed, which has been previously scrutinized and demonstrated to provide reliable insights into the optimized, electronic, and optical properties of carbon-based structures [32–35]. The selected 6-31G basis set [36] is utilized to strike a balance between computational accuracy and efficiency [37–39]. The Van der Waals interactions between the 2D 4AHEX membranes and the adsorbed molecules are considered by adding Grimme's dispersion correction (gd3) to the B3LYP functional [40]. For an in-depth analysis of optical

properties, time-dependent DFT calculations for the first fifty excited states are performed. Additionally, the electronic properties of 4AHEX and its decorated materials, both prior to and following the adsorption of creatinine and uric acid at edge and surface sites are investigated using the 6-31G/B3LYP level of theory. To further elucidate the electronic structure, the total density of states (TDOS) and partial density of states (PDOS) are computed employing the Multiwfn software [41].

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Optimized Structures Investigations

In this study, we present optimized molecular structures for finite graphene membranes by connecting four armchair hexagons that we simply call 4AHEX as seen in Fig.1 (a). the 2D membrane is then decorated with various transition metals at the edge and the surface, namely Co-edge, Co-surface, Mn-edge, Mn-surface, Ni-edge, and Ni-surface as illustrated in Fig. 1 (b-h). The introduction of metal atoms (Mn, Ni, Co) on both the edge and surface of 4AHEX induces subtle but noticeable changes in the molecular geometry, as evident from Table 1. For instance, examining the C1-C2 bond length, we observe variations from 1.404 Å in 4AHEX to 1.408 Å in Co-edg and 1.406 Å in Ni-surf. These nuanced alterations in bond lengths suggest localized effects of metal decoration. Analyzing bond angles, take the C1-C2-C3 angle as an example, where 4AHEX exhibits 122.251 degrees, while Co-surf and Ni-surf display 122.274 and 122.228 degrees, respectively. These values collectively confirm the SP^2 hybridization expected in these compounds. Crucially, the dihedral angles, such as C1-C2-C3-C4 and C2-C3-C4-C5, demonstrate the nonplanar nature of 4AHEX compounds and their decorated counterparts, with values deviating from planarity as observed in the side view of Fig. 1k. This comprehensive analysis, supported by specific values from Table 1, provides valuable insights into the structural modifications induced by metal decoration, contributing to a deeper understanding of the functional properties of these materials.

Fig. 1 Optimized molecular structures for 4AHEX and its based materials (a-h). Optimized structures of creatinine and uric acid (i and j). side view and label of 4AHEX (k and l).

Table 1 Some important quantum parameters like bond length (Å), dihedral, and bond angles (degrees) for 4AHEX and its based materials.

Designation	4AHEX	4AHEX-Co-edg	4AHEX-Co-surf	4AHEX-Mn-edg	4AHEX-Mn-surf	4AHEX-Ni-edg	4AHEX-Ni-surf
C1-C2	1.404	1.408	1.40	1.41	1.40	1.40	1.41
C3-C4	1.487	1.483	1.49	1.49	1.49	1.49	1.49
C5-C6	1.398	1.397	1.39	1.39	1.39	1.39	1.39
C1-C2-C3	122.25	121.97	122.27	122.28	122.28	122.23	122.12
C4-C5-C6	122.31	122.20	122.34	122.29	122.35	122.27	122.28
C1-C2-C3-C4	177.69	177.09	177.57	177.61	177.64	177.93	177.86
C2-C3-C4-C5	156.61	154.33	157.47	157.96	157.56	158.548	153.86

3.2 Structures stability

The investigation into the stability of 4AHEX and its derivatives involved the computation of their binding energies (BE). The BE was determined using the formula: $BE = (N_C E_C + N_H E_H + E_x N_x - E_t) / N_t$, where N_C , N_H , N_x , and N_t denote the numbers of carbon, hydrogen, decorated atoms, and the total number of atoms, respectively. Similarly, E_C , E_H , E_x , and E_t represent the total energies of carbon atoms, hydrogen atoms, decorated atoms, and the final compound, respectively. Our aim was to confirm the stability and characteristics of 4AHEX and its derivatives based on the calculated binding energies. The positive binding energies obtained, ranging from 7.450 to 7.491 eV, suggest the formation of 4AHEX and its associated compounds in a stable manner. When evaluating the binding energies for 4AHEX and its derivatives, such as 4AHEX-Co-edg, 4AHEX-Co-surf, 4AHEX-Mn-edg, 4AHEX-Mn-surf, 4AHEX-Ni-edg, and 4AHEX-Ni-surf, the values were found to be 7.485, 7.482, 7.448, 7.480, 7.452, 7.451, and 7.450 eV, respectively. These values indicate that the introduction of decorated transition atoms (Co, Mn, and Ni) at both the edge and surface increases the reactivity of 4AHEX decorated materials compared to the 4AHEX compound. Considering the calculated BE values, it can be concluded that the most stable molecular structure among the studied materials is 4AHEX when compared to the others. In summary, the investigation into the binding energies has confirmed the stable formation of 4AHEX and its derivatives, with the configuration of 4AHEX demonstrating the highest stability among the examined molecular structures. In contrast to previous studies on biphenyl boroxine covalent organic framework (COF) and its derivatives, which reported BE values in the range of 6-10 eV [18], our current findings indicate that 4AHEX and its based materials exhibit comparable stability. The calculated BE values for 4AHEX and its derivatives, ranging from 7.450 to 7.491 eV, clearly indicate their equivalent stability compared to biphenyl boroxine COF. This suggests that 4AHEX

and its based materials exhibit the same molecular stability when compared to the previously studied biphenyl boroxine COF and its derivatives [18].

In the realm of metal substitution within the 2D 4AHEX framework, the thermodynamic energy associated with metal adsorption can be comprehensively elucidated. Initially, the pristine 2D 4AHEX structure exists without any metal dopants, characterized by a specific energy denoted as the initial total energy (E_{initial}). Upon the introduction of metal atoms (Co, Mn, Ni) onto carbon sites within the 2D 4AHEX structure, interactions with the carbon atoms ensue, forming metal-carbon bonds and leading to a modified structure with incorporated metal dopants, resulting in a distinct total energy known as the final total energy (E_{final}). The substitution energy (ΔE_{ads}) is then calculated as the difference between the final total energy (E_{final}) and the initial total energy (E_{initial}). A negative ΔE_{ads} value signifies that the final state (with metal dopants) possesses lower energy compared to the initial state (without metal dopants), indicating the thermodynamic favorability of metal atom adsorption onto the carbon sites. Moreover, a more negative ΔE_{ads} value denotes a stronger binding affinity between the metal atoms and the carbon sites within the 2D 4AHEX structure, highlighting the energetically favored configurations of metal-incorporated 4AHEX membranes and thus indicating stable arrangements. The calculated ΔE_{ads} values for 4AHEX-Co-edg, 4AHEX-Co-surf, 4AHEX-Mn-edg, 4AHEX-Mn-surf, 4AHEX-Ni-edg, and 4AHEX-Ni-surf are -37603.981, -36582.455, -31296.205, -30275.980, -41020.330, and -39997.451 eV, respectively. In summary, the determination of ΔE_{ads} values offers crucial insights into the thermodynamic stability of metal adsorption onto carbon sites within 2D 4AHEX structures, aiding in evaluating the feasibility of metal substitution and elucidating the energetically preferred configurations of metal-decorated 4AHEX membranes.

3.3 Electronic investigations

In this study, we systematically investigated the electronic properties of 4AHEX and its Co, Mn, and Ni-decorated counterparts at both edges and surfaces, as illustrated in Fig. 2 (a-e) and Fig. 3 (a, and b). The calculated total and partial density of states (TDOS and PDOS) revealed a noticeable reduction in the energy gap (E_g) upon the introduction of Co, Mn, and Ni, with values of 2.88, 2.075, 1.857, 1.657, 1.730, 2.119, and 1.718 eV for 4AHEX, 4AHEX-Co-edg, 4AHEX-Co-surf, 4AHEX-Mn-edg, 4AHEX-Mn-surf, 4AHEX-Ni-edg, and 4AHEX-Ni-surf, respectively. This decrease in E_g is attributed to the emergence of HOMO and LUMO PDOS peaks associated with the transition elements, as depicted in Fig. 2 (a-e) and Fig. 3 (a, and b). Further analysis in Fig. 2 (f-j) and Fig. 3 (c and d) illustrates the localization of HOMO and LUMO orbitals on the C-C bond, select carbon atoms, and the Co, Mn, and Ni dopants. The resulting enhanced interaction between the C-C bond and these transition elements suggests a pivotal role in electron donation and acceptance. Electrostatic potential maps in Fig. 3 (e-j) reveal intriguing information about the electron distribution on the material surfaces, indicating potential electrophilic susceptibility of carbon atoms (depicted in yellow) and nucleophilic reactivity of hydrogen atoms (depicted in blue). These findings collectively suggest the feasibility of utilizing these structures as membranes for selective adsorption of uric acid and creatinine, given their distinctive electronic and electrostatic characteristics.

Fig. 2 TDOS/PDOS (a–e) and HOMO/LUMO representation (f–j) for 4AHEx, and it has surface and edge decorations made of Mn and Co.

Fig. 3 TDOS/PDOS (a and b), and HOMO/LUMO representation (c and d) for 4AHEx-Ni-edg and 4AHEx-Ni-surf. ESP for 4AHEx and its based materials (e-j).

3.4 Membrane Study of 4AHEx and Doped Materials

Fig. 4a illustrates the adsorption positions for creatinine and uric acid, as well as the doping positions for transition elements such as Co, Mn, and Ni. Specifically, positions 1 and 2 correspond to edge and surface adsorptions. In Figs. 4b-q, the optimized molecular structures for 4AHEx and its decorated atoms are presented after the adsorption of creatinine and uric acid at both edge and surface positions. The adsorption energy (E_a) is calculated using the formula $E_a = E_{(\text{sub-ads.})} - (E_{\text{sub.}}$

+ $E_{\text{ads.}}$), where $E_{(\text{sub-ads.})}$ represents the energy of the substrate after adsorbing creatinine and uric acid, $E_{\text{sub.}}$ is the energy of the substrate (4AHEX and its decorated materials), and $E_{\text{ads.}}$ is the energy of the adsorbate (creatinine or uric acid). The obtained results are summarized in Table 2. The consistently negative adsorption energy values (E_a), ranging from -0.833 to -2.810, indicate the favorable adsorption of creatinine and uric acid in various scenarios. Table 2 illustrates that the presence of decorated atoms (Co, Ni, and Mn) increases the E_a negative values, enhancing the adsorption of creatinine and uric acid on both the edge and surface of 4AHEX and its decorated materials. The adsorption process is supported by the reduction in the closest distance between the substrate and adsorbate ($d_{\text{sub-ads}}$), as shown in Table 2. In undecorated 4AHEX materials, the closest bond is formed between the hydrogen atom in the adsorbate (creatinine and uric acid) and carbon atoms on both the edge and surface, suggesting a hydrogen bond (C....H-C). After adsorption, the length of this bond decreases to 2.488, 2.912, 2.827, and 2.009 Å for 4AHEX-edg-creatinine, 4AHEX-surf-creatinine, 4AHEX-edg-uric acid, and 4AHEX-surf-uric acid, respectively, further supporting the adsorption process. In the case of decorated 4AHEX materials, the expected closest bond is (X....N) with a length in the range between 1.883 and 3.229 Å. The decrease in X....N bonds after the adsorption process confirms the effectiveness of adsorption. Mulliken charge calculations for undecorated 4AHEX materials reveal values for C atoms, while for decorated 4AHEX materials, values for decorated atoms X (Co, Mn, Ni) are collected in Table 2. The change in Mulliken charge of C for undecorated 4AHEX, and transition atom (X) for decorated 4AHEX, further supports the adsorption of uric acid and creatinine on both the edge and surface. Overall, this comprehensive analysis suggests that 4AHEX and its decorated materials effectively adsorb creatinine and uric acid on both edge and surface sites, as evidenced by reduced closest distances and changes in Mulliken charge. These findings indicate the promising potential of 4AHEX and its decorated materials as effective membranes, particularly notable for their ability to retain molecules post-adsorption, especially with uric acid and creatinine. The behavior of Co, Mn, and Ni-doped 4AHEX upon creatinine adsorption exhibits distinct trends in electron density redistribution. For Co and Mn dopants, a decrease in the Mulliken charge at the edge structure suggests a loss of electron density around these atoms, indicative of interaction with creatinine molecules acting as electron acceptors. Conversely, an increase in the Mulliken charge on the surface indicates a gain in electron density, likely due to creatinine molecules acting as electron donors, transferring electron density to the dopant atoms. Meanwhile, Ni dopants show a similar decrease in electron density on the surface after creatinine adsorption, suggesting electron redistribution through interaction with creatinine molecules.

Fig. 4. 4AHEX and its decorated molecules have an optimized molecular structure following adsorption at both surface and edge locations (b-q). locations where doing and absorption take place (a).

Table 2 The closest distance ($d_{\text{sub-ads}}$) between the substrate and the adsorbate before and after creatinine and uric acid adsorption at the surface and edge of all molecules under study is known as the adsorption energy (E_a). Mulliken charge (CH) of C in 4AHEX and the decorated atoms (X) at the edge and surface sites (Co, Mn, Ni).

compounds	E_a (eV)	$d_{\text{sub-ads}}$ (Å)		Mulliken CH of X or C	
		Before	After	Before	After
4AHEX-edg-creatinine	-0.833	3.179	2.844	-0.243	-0.036
4AHEX-surf-creatinine	-0.818	3.392	2.912	-0.030	-0.200
4AHEX-edg-uric acid	-1.053	3.353	2.827	-0.243	-0.041
4AHEX-surf-uric acid	-1.080	3.136	2.009	-0.0300	-0.310
4AHEX-Co-edg-creatinine	-1.728	3.037	2.080	0.678	0.589
4AHEX-Co-surf-creatinie	-2.133	3.011	2.011	0.752	0.808
4AHEX-Co-edg-uric acid	-1.242	3.825	3.229	0.678	0.773
4AHEX-Co-surf-uric acid	-1.913	2.606	2.009	0.752	0.790
4AHEX-Mn-edg-creatinine	-2.484	2.696	2.117	0.727	0.714
4AHEX-Mn-surf-creatinine	-2.603	2.961	2.055	0.937	1.035
4AHEX-Mn-edg-uric acid	-2.292	3.069	2.122	0.727	0.915
4AHEX-Mn-surf-uric acid	-1.192	2.233	2.272	0.937	0.964
4AHEX-Ni-edg-creatinine	-2.810	3.193	1.883	0.325	0.312
4AHEX-Ni-surf-creatinie	-1.267	3.042	2.278	0.646	0.602
4AHEX-Ni-edg-uric acid	-2.086	2.810	2.009	0.325	0.587
4AHEX-Ni-surf-uric acid	-1.497	3.212	2.127	0.646	0.696

3.4.1 Electronic investigations

In Figs. 5 (a-l) and Supplementary Fig. S1 (a-d), the graphical representations illustrate the HOMO and LUMO orbitals of both undecorated 4AHEX and decorated 4AHEX after the adsorption of creatinine and uric acid at both the edges and surfaces. The adsorption of one creatinine and uric acid molecule onto undecorated 4AHEX and decorated 4AHEX induces shifts in the positions of the HOMO and LUMO, with the extent of shift dependent on the specific adsorbate material. In undecorated 4AHEX and decorated 4AHEX, the HOMO and LUMO are localized on certain carbon atoms of the substrate. Interestingly, the adsorbate molecules creatinine and uric acid generally do not actively participate in the distribution of HOMO and LUMO, except in specific cases such as 4AHEX-Mn-surf-creatinine, 4AHEX-Mn-edg-uric acid, 4AHEX-Mn-surf-uric acid, and 4AHEX-Ni-surf-uric acid. In these instances, the adsorbate molecules actively contribute to the LUMO distribution, indicating strong adsorption compared to other cases, as depicted in Figures 5 (j-l) and Supplementary Fig. S1 (d). The calculated energy gap values for undecorated 4AHEX and decorated 4AHEX after the adsorption of creatinine and uric acid at both edges and surfaces are presented in Figures 5 (a-l) and Fig. S1. The observed changes in the energy gap

values of undecorated 4AHEX and decorated 4AHEX after adsorption suggest distinct electronic behaviors. Additionally, considering these electronic behaviors and molecular interactions, the studied materials exhibit potential membrane characteristics, emphasizing their suitability for applications involving selective adsorption or separation processes.

Fig. 5 HOMO/LUMO graphical depiction, the energy gap for 4AHEx, and decoration with Co and Mn following the adsorption of uric acid and creatinine at the surface and edge.

3.5 Optical investigations

Figures 6(a-d) illustrate the absorption spectra of 4AHEX, and its Co, Mn, and Ni decorated materials, both prior to and following the adsorption of creatinine and uric acid at edge and surface sites. The optical parameters, encompassing the calculated excited state (ES), maximum wavelength (λ_{max}), transition energy (TE), electronic transition (ET), oscillator strength (f), and transition coefficient (TC), are succinctly presented in Table 3. Upon scrutiny of Fig. 6a and the λ_{max} values in Table 3, it becomes evident that the adsorption of creatinine and uric acid at both edge and surface sites of 4AHEX induces a subtle shift toward longer wavelengths, commonly referred to as a redshift. Similarly, Figs. 6(b-d) reveals a red shift in the maximum absorption peak due to the presence of decorated atoms (Co, Mn, and Ni). Nevertheless, during creatinine and uric acid adsorption on decorated 4AHEX (Fig. 6b-d), some shifts are directed towards the red end of the spectrum, while others exhibit a blue shift. For instance, examining 4AHEX-Co-edge in Table 3, the maximum absorption peak (λ_{max}) shifts to 447.02 nm with a transition from H-1 to L+7, accompanied by an oscillator strength (f) of 0.165. This signifies a specific electronic transition occurring during the adsorption of creatinine and uric acid. Furthermore, for 4AHEX-Mn-surf, the maximum absorption wavelength (λ_{max}) shifts to 573.69 nm with a transition from H-2 to L and an associated oscillator strength (f) of 0.094. This shift underscores the influence of Mn decoration on the absorption spectra during creatinine and uric acid adsorption. Table 3 also elucidates the optical parameters for 4AHEX and its decorated materials under various scenarios. Notably, in the case of 4AHEX-Ni-edg-uric acid, the λ_{max} is 549.57 nm with a transition from H to L+2, and the oscillator strength (f) is 0.164. These values accentuate the nuances in electronic transitions during uric acid adsorption on Ni-decorated 4AHEX at the edge site. Furthermore, insights into the electronic structure changes during adsorption processes are gleaned from the calculated excited state (ES), transition energy (TE), and transition coefficient (TC). A more in-depth exploration of these parameters would enhance our comprehension of the optical behavior and electronic transitions inherent in the investigated materials.

In addition to the detailed optical investigations, it is imperative to underscore the practical implications of these materials as potential candidates for membrane applications. The observed shifts in absorption spectra and electronic transitions during adsorption point to dynamic interactions at both edge and surface sites, suggesting the suitability of 4AHEX and its decorated materials for membrane-based applications. The discernible redshifts in absorption peaks indicate changes in the electronic structure of the materials upon adsorption, a feature that could influence their affinity for specific molecules, such as creatinine and uric acid. Consequently, these materials emerge as promising contenders for membrane applications, with potential applications in water purification, medical diagnostics, and other fields where selective molecular separation is paramount. Moreover, the distinctive characteristics exhibited by decorated materials, exemplified by 4AHEX-Co-edg and 4AHEX-Mn-surf, during the adsorption process further highlight their utility. The unique electronic transitions and associated parameters provide valuable information regarding the selectivity and efficiency of these materials in capturing target molecules.

Fig. 6(a) shows the 4AHEX absorption spectra both before and after the uric acid and creatinine were adsorbed on the surface and along the edge (b), The 4AHEX absorption spectra prior to and following surface and edge Co decorating, as well as following surface and edge uric acid and creatinine adsorption on 4AHEX-Co (c) The 4AHEX absorption spectra before and after the surface and edge Mn decorating, as well as following the adsorption of uric acid and creatinine on the 4AHEX-Mn surface. (d) The absorption spectra of 4AHEX before and after uric acid and creatinine adsorption on 4AHEX-Ni, as well as surface and edge Ni decorating.

Table 3 The calculated excited state (ES), maximum wavelength (λ_{\max}), transition energy (TE), electronic transition (ET), oscillator strength (f), and transition coefficient (TC) for 4AHEX, its decorated materials before and after the adsorption of creatinine and uric acid at both edge and surface.

Compounds	ES	λ_{\max} (nm)	TE (eV)	ET	f	TC
4AHEX	18	437.56	2.834	H→L+8	3.813	0.343
4AHEX-Co-edg	34	447.02	2.774	H-1→L+7	0.165	0.310
4AHEX-Co-surf	23	574.99	2.156	H→L+2	0.178	0.450
4AHEX-Mn-edg	40	464.64	2.668	H-2→L+3	0.751	0.335
4AHEX-Mn-surf	25	573.69	2.161	H-2→L	0.094	0.602
4AHEX-Ni-edg	17	581.59	2.132	H→L+3	0.181	0.212
4AHEX-Ni-surf	26	448.63	2.607	H→L+8	1.150	0.276
4AHEX-edg-creatinine	19	440.64	2.814	H→L+6	0.159	0.334
4AHEX-surf-creatinine	18	442.68	2.801	H→L+8	2.795	0.131
4AHEX-edg-uric acid	18	443.35	2.797	H→L+7	2.100	0.153
4AHEX-surf-uric acid	19	443.48	2.796	H→L+5	0.986	0.126
4AHEX-Co-edg-creatinine	33	449.27	2.760	H-3→L+2	1.035	0.488
4AHEX-Co-surf-creatinie	25	569.34	2.178	H-1→L	0.093	0.404
4AHEX-Co-edg-uric acid	35	452.86	2.769	H-2→L+3	1.120	0.295
4AHEX-Co-surf-uric acid	25	570.76	2.172	H→L+9	0.176	0.407
4AHEX-Mn-edg-creatinine	37	451.83	2.744	H→L+11	0.461	0.154
4AHEX-Mn-surf-creatinine	25	574.86	2.157	H-1→L+2	0.103	0.708
4AHEX-Mn-edg-uric acid	37	456.14	2.718	H→L+8	0.830	0.161
4AHEX-Mn-surf-uric acid	21	581.49	2.132	H-1→L+2	0.140	0.221
4AHEX-Ni-edg-creatinine	23	605.95	2.046	H→L+3	0.278	0.120
4AHEX-Ni-surf-creatinie	34	446.01	2.780	H-5→L+1	1.025	0.368
4AHEX-Ni-edg-uric acid	24	549.57	2.256	H→L+2	0.164	0.160
4AHEX-Ni-surf-uric acid	37	453.82	2.732	H-1→L+6	0.782	0.421

3.6 NCI Unravels creatinine/uric acid-Substrate Interactions

Non-covalent interaction (NCI) analysis serves as a valuable tool for examining various interaction types, including hydrogen bonding, van der Waals forces, strong attractive forces, and repulsive steric interactions [42]. The primary goal of NCI analysis is to gain insights into the nature and characteristics of these interactions. This analysis is presented through a two-dimensional reduced density gradient (RDG) and a three-dimensional iso-surface. Plots of non-covalent interactions and

RDG against $(\text{sign } \lambda_2)\rho$ are generated [43]. For robust interactions between creatinine or uric acid and 4AHEX and its decorated substrates molecule, the $(\text{sign } \lambda_2)\rho$ value should be less than zero, indicating attraction, while repulsion is indicated by a value greater than zero. In the 3D NCI analysis, various color patches are employed to represent different interaction types. Yellow and green patches signify van der Waals interactions, blue patches denote strong attractive interactions, and red patches indicate steric repulsion. Points of attractive interaction are observed at higher density values ($\rho > 0.01$ au), while repulsive interaction points occur at lower density values ($\rho < 0.01$). The 3D images and 2D plots of NCI analyses are depicted in Fig. 7 (a-f). For creatinine and uric acid adsorbed on 4AHEX and its decorated substrates, green patches are evident between creatinine or uric acid and the substrate, as illustrated in the side and front views of Fig. 6 (a-f). These complexes exhibit significant van der Waals interactions. All optimized complexes display van der Waals interaction spikes at $\rho < 0.01$ au in the 2D graph, while repulsion interactions spike at $\rho > 0.01$ au. High-density green spikes appear in the region of $(\text{sign } \lambda_2)\rho$ values from 0.00 to -0.01 au with green patches for creatinine or uric acid-adsorbed 4AHEX and its decorated substrates, indicating a central role of van der Waals interactions in creatinine and uric acid adsorption.

Fig. 7 (a-f) NCI surfaces and scatter graph (2D graph) of 4AHEx-edg-creatinine, 4AHEx-Co-edg-creatinine, 4AHEx-Co-edg-uric, 4AHEx-Co-surf-creatinine, 4AHEx-Co-surf-uric acid, 4AHEx-Mn-edg-creatinine, and 4AHEx-Mn-surf-uric acid.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this study provides a thorough understanding of the properties and interactions of metal-decorated graphene membranes (4AHEX) with creatinine and uric acid. The optimized structures revealed subtle modifications induced by metal decoration, influencing the molecular geometry. Stability analysis confirmed the stable formation of these compounds, with 4AHEX demonstrating the highest stability. Electronic investigations showcased a reduction in the energy gap upon metal decoration, indicating increased reactivity. Membrane studies demonstrated the favorable adsorption of creatinine and uric acid, supported by negative adsorption energies, and reduced closest distances. Optical investigations and non-covalent interaction analysis provided insights into dynamic interactions and the role of van der Waals forces in adsorption processes. These findings collectively emphasize the potential of 4AHEX and its decorated derivatives for selective adsorption applications, particularly in the detection of creatinine and uric acid, opening avenues for their utilization in various fields, including medical diagnostics.

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Data availability All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article.

Code availability: Not applicable

Declarations

Ethical Approval: This article does not contain any studies involving animals performed by any of the authors.

Consent to Participate: This article does not contain any studies involving animals performed by any of the authors.

Consent to Publish: All authors mentioned in the manuscript have given consent for submission and subsequent publication of the manuscript.

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Fig. S1 HOMO/LUMO graphical depiction, the energy gap for 4AHEX, and Ni decoration following the adsorption of uric acid and creatinine at the surface and edge.